

Uncontracted: Reimagining work and identity in higher education's third space

Joanne Caldwell

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845373>

Scan this code for a link to the podcast on Spotify.

Provocation

Given the ongoing shifts in professional identity and practice within higher education, the symposium provided an opportunity to critically consider the archaic structure of employment contracts in the sector. I proposed that there is scope to re-examine the traditional bifurcation between academic and professional services roles. Rather than maintaining distinct contracts for these groups, institutions might instead adopt a unified employment model in which roles are defined by job descriptions specifying tasks and responsibilities, thereby negating the need for categorical differentiation. While such a model presents clear challenges in the United Kingdom, particularly in relation to Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA) reporting, Research Excellence Framework (REF) submissions, and other statutory requirements that currently necessitate definitional distinctions, the session focused deliberately on exploring possibilities rather than practicalities.

The discussion was grounded in a 2024 podcast (Caldwell, 2024a) that examined the notion of identity among professional services staff and its relationship to my own research in this area (Caldwell, 2021, 2022a, 2022b, 2024b). During the session, participants were invited to reflect on the perceived value of work undertaken by professional services and academic staff, and to consider the potential of a third space employment model.

Context: The Third Space Professional

The concept of the third space has been a topic of scholarly discussion for several decades. Bhabha (2004, p. 2) conceptualised it as “the overlap and displacement of domains of difference,” describing it as an in-between space that moves beyond singular or binary notions of identity. This third space provides “the terrain for elaborating strategies of selfhood” (Bhabha, 2004, p. 2), enabling the emergence of hybrid identities that challenge established norms. Within this liminal context, “new signs of identity, and innovative sites of collaboration and contestation” (Bhabha, 2004, p. 2) are made possible. Bhabha further contends that the third space disrupts cultural conventions by existing as “neither the one nor the other” (Bhabha, 2004, p. 37). However, for this form of hybridity to be legitimised, difference and otherness must first be acknowledged. This theoretical framing offers a useful lens for examining the shifting boundaries between academic and administrative roles within higher education.

In recent years, the limited body of literature addressing the identities of professional services staff has increasingly centred on the emergence of the third space professional. The notion of the third

space professional in higher education was developed through Whitchurch's extensive research, which identified a new category of hybrid staff who operate across the traditional academic and administrative divide (2004, 2006, 2008a, 2008b, 2009a, 2012, 2018).

The career trajectories of professional services staff are no longer characterised by linear progression. Instead, individuals now move fluidly across departments, undertake secondments, and pursue opportunities across institutions and the broader sector (Whitchurch, 2009b; Veles & Carter, 2016). Such transitions, while offering new opportunities, may also lead to a loss of professional identity and a sense of displacement, as individuals perceive themselves as not fully belonging to the academic or professional services domains (Whitchurch, 2009a; Veles & Carter, 2016; Akerman, 2020).

Over the past fifteen years, scholarly attention has shifted from examining the functions of professional services staff as a support mechanism for academics and institutions to exploring their evolving professional identities. Increasingly, professional services staff are recognised as a distinct and integral workforce, whose roles are becoming more fluid and blended rather than strictly delineated (Vere et al., 2024).

Rethinking contractual boundaries: The potential for institutional employment models

Participant responses revealed significant variation shaped by individual experience and institutional context. Many identified the perceived divide between academic and professional services staff as stemming not only from contractual distinctions but also from disparities in the visibility of their work. Reference was made to the Teaching Excellence Framework (TEF) and REF as mechanisms that privilege visible, quantifiable outputs, as well as to HESA reporting practices, which capture data exclusively for academic staff. Participants argued that these structures render the work of professional services staff largely invisible, reinforcing their lack of recognition and sustaining expectations that they will continually assume additional responsibilities and initiatives.

Participants highlighted the persistent hierarchies and disparities within higher education employment structures. One noted that teaching-only contracts are frequently perceived as less prestigious than research-focused appointments, reflecting the ongoing prioritisation of visible research outputs. In contrast, many professional services and third space staff occupy highly specialised, senior, or research-active roles, contributing substantively to policy formulation, strategic initiatives, and the broader institutional direction. Participants emphasised the importance of recognising and making visible these contributions, observing that “contracts that recognise those who are developing skills across multiple areas could be beneficial.”

A particularly salient theme concerned the absence of recognition of research and data generation undertaken by professional services staff. Categorising staff solely according to contractual type risks narrowing the perceived scope of expertise within the sector. Unlike academic staff, professional services staff typically lack workload models that explicitly allocate time for research, constraining their capacity to engage in scholarly activities. As one participant noted, “The idea of research time for third space professionals is such a crucial idea... I can provide some grant funding to third space professionals for research, but time is the limiting factor.” Consequently, the

absence of dedicated research time often necessitates that professional services staff undertake research outside of contracted hours, a practice that can adversely impact their work–life balance. Participants argued that stronger collaboration between academic and professional services colleagues, alongside better integration of professional services-generated data within institutional research ecosystems, could yield valuable insights to inform policy and enhance both staff and student experiences. These findings align with Verney and Curtis (2025), who advocate institutional mechanisms to support professional services staff and dismantle cultural barriers.

Although developing a unified higher education contract presents significant structural and regulatory challenges, the discussion underscored that expanding opportunities for staff to work across traditional boundaries is both timely and necessary. Empowering professional services staff to engage in research and collaborative practice not only enhances their professional development but also enriches the collective knowledge base that underpins universities' educational mission.

Final reflections

Participating in the Third Space Symposium and engaging with its online content was a novel and enriching experience. Given the international scope of the symposium, it was initially uncertain whether a discussion focused on higher education contracts, particularly within a UK context, would resonate with all participants. Although the number of responses was limited, the insights provided were valuable in exploring perspectives on the notion of a third space and the concept of an institutional contract of work. The feedback also revealed the frustrations experienced by professional services staff regarding how they are perceived within the academy, alongside their strong desire for recognition of the breadth and depth of their contributions. Within the UK, stringent reporting requirements necessitate clear distinctions between professional groups in higher education. However, considering the sector's ongoing evolution, there is potential for future reconsideration of employment contract structures. I intend to pursue further research in this area to contribute to that discussion.

References

- Akerman, K. (2020). Invisible imposter: identity in institutions. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 24(4), 1–5.
- Bhabha, H. (2004). *The location of culture* (2nd ed.), Routledge.
- Caldwell, J. (2021). Perceptions of identity in higher education: Professional services and academic staff. EdD Thesis. Manchester Metropolitan University. <https://e-space.mmu.ac.uk/629210/>
- Caldwell, J. (2022a). Professional identity and professional services staff: understanding and impact. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 26(4), 1–8.
- Caldwell, J. (2022b). “People don’t understand what our role is, it is definitely seen as an inferior job to an academic”: Perceptions on relationships between professional services and academic staff in the UK. *Journal of Higher Education Management*, 37(1), 24–35.
- Caldwell, J. (2024a). “Non-Academic”: Labelled by what you’re not. In *Knowledge Exchange: Deep-Dive*. <https://open.spotify.com/episode/30MtITFUxNBwdKrhLooHPK>

- Caldwell, J. (2024b). Nomenclature in higher education: “non-academic” as a construct. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 46(5), 507–522.
- Veles, N., & Carter, M.-A. (2016). Imagining a future: changing the landscape for third space professionals in Australian higher education institutions. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 38(5), 519–533.
- Vere, K., Verney, C., & Webster-Deakin, T. (2024). Crossing and dismantling boundaries: recognising the value of professional staff within higher education. *London Review of Education*, 22.1.9.
- Verney, C., & Curtis, H. J. (2025). Enabling an inclusive research culture for higher education professional services researchers. *Exchanges: The Warwick Research Journal*, 12(3), 50–71.
- Whitchurch, C. (2004). Administrative managers – a critical link. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 58(4), 280–298.
- Whitchurch, C. (2006). Who do they think they are? The changing identities of professional administrators and managers in UK higher education. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 28(2), 159–171.
- Whitchurch, C. (2008a). Beyond administration and management: Reconstructing the identities of professional staff in UK higher education. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 30(4), 375–386.
- Whitchurch, C. (2008b). Shifting identities and blurring boundaries: The emergence of third space professionals in UK higher education. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 62(4), 377–396.
- Whitchurch, C. (2009a). Progressing professional careers in UK higher education. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 13(1), 3–10.
- Whitchurch, C. (2009b). The rise of the blended professional in higher education: a comparison between the United Kingdom, Australia and the United States. *Higher Education*, 58(3), 407–418.
- Whitchurch, C. (2012). *Reconstructing identities in higher education: The rise of ‘third space’ professionals*. Routledge.
- Whitchurch, C. (2018). Being a higher education professional today: Working in a third space. In C. Bossu & N. Brown (Eds.), *Professional and support staff in higher education* (pp. 11–21). Springer Nature.

About the author

Joanne Caldwell

Salford Business School

Dr Joanne Caldwell FAHEP FHEA is Joint Editor of *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education* and works as School Business Manager at Salford Business School, University of Salford. Her doctoral research explored the relationships of professional services staff with academic colleagues.